

SECTION III
COMBINATION OF LANGUAGE AND QUALITY EDUCATION IN TEACHING
METHODS

METHODS OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract:

The present article is devoted to analysis of different activities and classroom tasks which will develop student's speaking skills and create good atmosphere for communication of students both with teacher and each other. These simple activities can be used as warning-up at the beginning of English lessons and as filler at the end of the classes. They will motivate students, develop their communicative competence.

Key words: communicative competence, speaking skills, activities, logical thinking, creative skills, methodology of teaching.

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The significant role of a language in social surrounding, its interaction with human's mind, complicatedness of its structures defined the specifics of language as a systemic-structural unit. Being the main instrument of communication, language has a diversity of means for nominating objects of the world and expressing thoughts and feelings. Really, language fulfills its main function – to serve as a means of communication [1, p. 54].

The concept of competence in the system of modern education is becoming especially topical in connection with the intensive development of information technologies, which has led to fundamental changes in the sphere of economic activity and everyday life of people and has caused an increase in the need for training highly qualified, erudite and initiative personnel.

By competence in this work, we understand the formed ability and readiness of a person to perform activities implemented through a set of competencies – “the integrity of knowledge, skills and abilities that ensure the professional activity of a specialist” [2, p. 23].

Speaking is one of the 4 main language skills, so teaching speaking and improving learners' speaking skills plays an important role in teaching process. Here are some simple methods of improving students' speaking skills.

Activity 1. Prepare short speech telling

This activity should be used at first lessons of English for getting better introduction with students and a new teacher. Students should prepare speech which contains the following information and share it with groupmates:

1. Your name and surname.
2. Where are you from (birthplace).
3. School graduated from in....
4. Your hobby.
5. Your motto.

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6. Your dream and main aim in your life.

Activity 2. Rate according to degree of importance

This activity helps to disclose inner world of students. They will be interested in listening to each other's answers.

I and my health, lifestyle

Education

Job and career

Religion and morality

Relatives

Family

Money

Friends and entertainments

Activity 3. Make up dialogues in the frame of cultural communication

These are complicated situations when speakers are either nervous or anxious. Give these topics to students. 5 minutes will be enough for their preparation.

You are late for a date with your friend who was waiting for you for more than 30 minutes

You have forgotten your spouse's birthday

You have occasionally torn someone's book or notebook

You have bought a spoiled foodstuff in supermarket and give it back

You have flooded your neighbors' apartment

Activity 4. Using so/because

This activity will be useful after explaining structures of compound and complex sentences with "so" and "because". One and the same sentences should be used with both of conjunctions. It's better to use this activity with two groups of students, one group will be responsible for "so", another for "because".

My sister is a little bit fat

That restaurant was very expensive

We didn't stay at this hotel

We went to the countryside on Sunday

I like to read detective stories

She likes yellow colour

His salary was reduced

My neighbours don't use meat

Activity 5. Matching tasks.

Matching tasks are very interesting for students. This is one of the simple examples "professions and verbs"

Builder

grow

Teacher

defend

Taxi-driver

manage

Cook

sew

Gardener

make deal

Military man

teach

Director

count

Doctor

take ... by car

Baker

boil

Tailor / dress maker

treat

Businessman

construct

Economist

bake

Activity 6. Language styles

First a teacher should explain language styles and then give following examples for students to classify:

Official style

Scientific style

Publicistic style

Belle-lettre style

Colloquial style

(newspaper article, telephone conversation, dissertation political speech, discussion of football match, novel, interview with employer, abstract of dissertation, dialogue in shopping process, fairy tale, advertisement)

Activity 7. Telephone conversation

Students will sit with their back to each other and imitate telephone conversation in different roles. Here are some examples of them:

Teacher and pupil's parent

Wrong call

Food deliver from restaurant

Call for ambulance

Call for inviting guests

Activity 8. Judge

This activity is used for discussing difficult problematic situations and to solve them. For example, there are only 2 airway tickets left and 4 persons need them. Students will express their opinion for the situation.

16 years old girl

28 years old priest

35 years old widow who has 3 children

56 years old experienced doctor

Activity 9. Odd-one-out

This activity is excellent for developing logical thinking. One of the words is extra in the list. Students should find it and explain why one word is odd in the list:

assistant teacher, senior teacher, doctor of science, professor

bachelor, master, doctor, professor

flute, drum, piano, rubab

soup, cutlet, fried potato, chicken

tea, coffee, milk, brendi

bus, trolleybus, tram, underground

rose, carnation, sunflower, orchid

smart board, smart TV, smart phone, smart notebook

dollar, money, rouble, pound-sterling

happy, clever, obstinate, responsible

Activity 10. The riddle

This activity is very interesting. It develops students' logical thinking, broaden their outlook. For example, the following riddle is based on the following: one very poor man earned 10 cents a day. And it was enough to pay his debt, save for future and even throw out of window. He lived with his old mother, young son and daughter. The questions is: how is it possible? Students should give their point of view and explain the answer of the riddle.

References:

[1]. Tan O. S. *Thinking Skills, Creativity and Problem-Based Learning*. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2000. – 298 p.

- [2]. Vygotsky L. *Mind in society*. – Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, 2013. – 254 p.
- [3]. <http://www.trainingindustry.com>